

LOW POWER HIGH SPEED HANS CARLSON ADDER USING SPST

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ABSTRACT

The concept of SPST is to segregate the arithmetic units into Most significant Part (MSP) & Least significant Part (LSP), where MSP doesn't affect most of computation results. Efficient adders are beneficial in the arithmetic circuit design. Ripple carry adder was found to have lowest gate count but maximum delay. To address the area and delay, a high speed low power Han Carlson adder adopting SPST is proposed in this part of process. Hans Carlson adder's is coalescence of two designs comprising Koggestone and the Brent-Kung construction. The Xilinx- Vivado tool was used to simulate the results. In contrast with the other SPST adders, the proposed SPST Han Carlson Adder's has a lower delay imbibing of 450ps and an area of 7 cells or area.

Keywords: Han Carlson adders, Spurious Power Suppression Technique, Xilinx-Vivado, Parallel-Prefix Adders.

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1.INTRODUCTION

Binary addition is one of the preminent functions of arithmetic in contemporary digital approaches. The Han-Carlson adder was presented by Han and Carlson to achieve compromise between logic depth, number of computational nodes, and connectivity. Han Carlson adder is a coalescence of Brent-kung and Kogge- Stone adders.

A 16-bit parallel prefix adder designed by Han- Carlson uses a single Brent-Kung stage to compute the initial stage of the parallel prefixes, three Kogge- Stone stages, and a final Brent-Kung stage for the final stage of prefix computation.

This architecture provides speed within the reach of the Kogge Stone adder. All parallel prefix adders undergo comparable additional processing following the calculation of the parallel prefixes.

Spurious transitions are unwanted transitions which transpires in the digital circuit nevertheless intended or expected to. They are often caused by timing problems and undesirable redundant hardware in the circuit. The switching action that takes place in the circuit during these unpleasant transitions is what descends to. As we know, energy is consumed during, and the energy generated during the altercations is known as spurious energy. In circuits like adders or multipliers, the SPST comprises of Detecting Logic (DL) block that governs the swaps in the resultant data-bits occurs. When a piece of data does not affect the circuit's result, it is latched to elude wasteful transitions inner side of the processing units. The envisioned speed would be accomplished. To reduce dynamic power usage, this subsection recommended a low power adder and subtractor based on SPST. In SPST, the LSP and MSP are the 2 equally weighted components of the subtraction and addition operation.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

To build the Hans Carlson adder utilizing SPST, a significant amount of effort antiquated into research of the SPST with Han Carlson. The SPST design for combinational VLSI designs for multimedia or DSP an application [1]. The most and least cardinal components (MSP and LSP) of intent designs are sundered into two slices in the proposed SPST, which tetraplegic the MSP when it has no bearing on the conclusions of the computation. An adder is a circuit that calculates the summation of two or three (half adders or full adders) inputs [2]. An adders with n stages could be made by cascading a full adder.

The term "parallel adder" refers to this combining adder arrangement. The article [3] discusses an eight-bit adder that consists of 3 different constructions: a parallel adder, a conventional Carry Look Ahead adder, and an SPST carry look ahead (CLA) adder. In paper [4], the SPST technique, that is controlled by the detecting unit using an AND gate, can be used to achieve high adder speed. The carry choice adder would be among the comprehensively used adders in arithmetic operation. The high- speed adder used in VLSI architectures uses quite a lot of space and energy.

The SPST is designed in a different way that overlooks needless proceedings and annihilates overlapping bits. The document [5] describes how to prevent the unwanted transitions. This influences the components that carry out changes and generate data, and it depletes the unwanted flow of power in adders. Adder is utilized hence processors used for addition are required. The preceding multipliers employed a serial adding technique that increased the complexity of the system by processing data bit by bit using simple serial adders such the carry forward adder, ripple carry adder (RCA), and carry save adder. In order to mitigate such errors, they are using parallel prefix adders (PPA) which function more quickly developed an SPST-based booth encoder using a power SPST adder to mount a high-speed low power multiplier.

The two Brent-Kung stage at the start & finish of each section and Kogge-Stone stage in the center. Thereafter in order to quote the Hybrid Han-Carlson layout midsection [10]. The hybrid Han Carlson adder is a new design that reduces complexity, silicon area, and power while marginally increasing delay. The binary addition issue can be solved very effectively with PPA, those are ideal for FPGA implementation. Prefix computations are an effective way to express carry propagation in binary addition [11]. The complexity, space, and consumed power of the reformed hybrid Han-Carlson adder are all greatly reduced.

3. EXISTING METHODOLOGY

The use of Brent Kung adders is common for highly efficient computations. To perform the addition operation, the parallel Brent-kung prefix adder is utilized. It is a tree structure since the arithmetic operation must be completed on it. Grey and black cells are included by the Brent-kung adder. [12] Individual black cell contains 2 AND gates and OR gate, while each grey cell has an AND gate. P_i stands for propagate and is made of a single AND gate from equation 1. Where “ g_i ” is generate and comprises of one AND, one OR gate in equation 2.

$$p_i = A_i \wedge B_i \quad [1]$$

$$g_i = A_i \& B_i \quad [2]$$

First black cell in equation 3 composed of one AND gate and OR gate where “ G_i ” represented as carry generated.

$$G_i = p_i \vee (g_i \& cin) \quad [3]$$

Spurious transitions occur in digital electronics while being in adverted and startling. Timing issues and objectionable superfluous hardware in the circuit are the root cause of the errors. In relevance, the displacement activity that matriculates in the circuit when these unwanted transitions occur. These transitions consume ample amount of energy, and the energy that comes from them are called as Spurious Energies.

In SPST attribute a DL block that deliberates whether there is a distinction in the resultant data-bits in circuits like multiplier/adder. Fervent irrelevant transitions within the processing units, a shiver of the data is latched which exempt the circuits outcome. Thus, the coveted speed will be acquired.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

By combining two outlines that is a Kogge Stone, which requires $\log_2 n$ stage, and the Brent-Kung construction, which requires $2\log_2 n - 1$ stage but requires less space for the combinational circuit than the Kogge-Stone layout T. Han and D.A. Carlson have created a hybrid parallel prefix adder [11].

16-bits parallel prefix adders designed by Han-Carlson utilizes one Brent-Kung stage to compute the initial stage of the parallel prefixes, 3 Kogge-Stone stages, and a final Brent Kung stage for the accomplishment stage of prefix computation. All parallel prefix adders undergo comparable additional processing following the estimation of the parallel prefixes. Fig 1 depicts the prefix computation stage of a 16-bits Han Carlson adder.

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Fig. 1 Low-power brunt Kung adder model adopting SPST.

Fig. 2 16-bit Parallel prefix Han-Carlson adder.

The edifice of the Han-Carlson Adder and several planning parameters were investigated. And researched several Prefix cells those are utilized in the design, and their equations [12] as illustrated in the Fig 2 for pre-processing parallel prefix stage in order to estimate, produce and propagate.

$$g = a \text{ and } b \quad \& \quad p = a \text{ xor } b$$

Fig. 3 Logical diagram for black, grey and buffer cells

The binary addition problem is expressed as follows: $A = a_{n-1}, a_{n-2}, \dots, a_0$ are given n-bit augends. $B = b_{n-1}, b_{n-2}, \dots, b_0$ is an n-bit addend. Compute the n-bit sum $S = s_{n-1}, s_{n-2}, \dots, s_0$. Allow us to demonstrate as C_i the execution of the i-th bit. The C_i and S_i is calculated as follows.

$$s_i = a_i \oplus b_i \oplus c_{i-1}$$

$$C_i = a_i b_i + a_i c_{i-1} + b_i c_{i-1}$$

As we utilize 3 stages in prefix addition to record the sum preprocessing, prefix-processing, and post arranging. The generated g_i and p_i signal in pre-handling is given below.

$$g_i = a_i \cdot b_i$$

$$p_i = a_i \oplus b_i$$

The constrain $g_i = 1$ indicates as carry will be produced at bit-i. Since $P_i = 1$ indicates that a carry traversed between bit-i. The generate and propagate approach could be expanded to a category of consecutive bits from bit-k to bit-i (with $k < i$) in the subsequent:

$$G_{[i:k]} = \begin{cases} g_i & \text{if } i = k \\ g_{[i:j]} + P_{[i:j]} G_{[j:k]} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$P_{[i:k]} = \begin{cases} p_i & \text{if } i = k \\ P_{[i:j]} P_{[j:k]} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where: $i \geq l \geq j \geq k$.

The scenario $g[i:k]$ describes the generation of a carry through the block k-1, whereas the scenario $p[i:k]$ denotes the propagation of the carry through the block. As a result, for any bit i and C_i can be stated as follows:

$$C_i = g[i:0] + p[i:0]c_{-1}$$

Fig. 4 Spurious transitions in the DSP computing.

To minimize dynamic power usage, this subsection recommended a low power adder and subtractors positioned on SPST. In SPST the Most Significant Part and Least Significant Part are the two equally weighted components of the summation and subtraction operations. Both Latch B and A in the MSP adder /subtractor serve as the Data Controlling Unit for the adder two operand.

The Sign Extension (SE) and MSP addition circuits are turned on or off by the detection logic circuit. The logic gates for generating the carry signal output would be deleted from the SPST architecture since the output carry from the (MSP) Most Significant Part is not required for the estimation that follows.

Fig. 5 Propound SPST Han Carlson adder design.

Fig. 6 Detection Logic (DL) circuit.

The close signal decides how to latch the MSP of the operands. To mitigate switching power consumed, the AND gate locks the MSP data when Close is equal to one and changes data of the MSP to 0 while Close is equal to 0. The DL block significantly temporizes the signals to create the Close, Carry ctrl, and Sign Signals. Figures 5, 6.

Three probable SPST cases are examined in the section that follows. The close signal decides how to latch the operands of the MSP. To reduce switching power consumption, data of MSP is latched by using and gates when Close is equal to 1 and becomes zero when Close is 0. The DL circuit slightly the signals will be delayed creating the Close signals, Sign-signals and Carry control signal Fig 4 and Fig 5. The analysis that follows is performed on three prospective cases of the SPST.

1. MSP is disabled via of the detector logic circuit: The SE unit is currently operating directly. The estimations in the Most Significant Part (MSP) circuit should be by passed insignificance of the offset the delay introduced by the DL circuit and account for the MSP outputs.
2. The DL unit switches on very important: Before data of the MSP can be latched through, the DL circuit should provide a Close signal in order to actuate the latches. As a result, the detecting logic circuit's delay exert influence on the adder's overall delay.
3. The route governed by the combinational component (that is the subtractor or adder) remains intact, therefore the detection logic's previous decision regarding whether to switch on or off the MSP has no effect. The close signal decides how to latch the MSP of the operands.

To mark down switching power consumed, the AND gate locks the MSP data when Close is 1 and changes data of the MSP to zero when Close = 0. The signed loading of bytes (we will be taking eight bits using the load byte instruction) and half words (let us take 16 bits using the load half word instruction) are utilized with the sign extension circuit, which operates on the principle of SE. The most (MSP)important bit is fed to the abiding bits as part of the sign extension process. For unsigned loading, zero extension is applied.

Fig. 7 (a) gated data latch circuit (b) sign extension circuit

5.RESULTS

The two 16-bit SPST HCA design which is integrated with detection logic (DL) and Sign Extension (SE) top module schematic is shown in Fig 8.

Fig. 8 Schematic diagram of SPST HCA Adder

Fig. 9. Depicts how SPST HCA adder can be used in order to generate the results of simulation of 2-16-bit addition. Table1 gives the area, power and timing analyzed for different SPST adders.

Fig. 9 The simulation outcome in Xilinx Vivado software.

Table I. COMPARISON OF RESULTS

Parameter	SPST ripple carry adder	SPST Brent kung adder	SPST Han Carlson adder
Power	(nw) 10848.179	(nw) 5448	(nw) 5256
Area	8	7	7
Cell count	71	48	73
Timing	742ps	580ps	450ps

6. CONCLUSION

Regarding power, delay and area between other parallel prefix Adders, the Han-Carlson adder is the forerunner because it gives an excellent trade-off between fan-out and numerous logic cells. As SPST Adder reduces power dissipation caused by switching by eliminating setbacks. The structural framework presumed would be designed with Xilinx Vivado. The 16-bit SPST HCA consumes 5256nW of power and 450ps of delay. As a result, these ports imply that the SPST Han Carlson Adder outperforms other SPST adders in relation to consumed power and delay (timing).

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